

Effect of Polypropylene Fibers on Concrete with Partial Replacement of Cement by Lime Sludge

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Abstract: Concrete is one of the most widely used construction materials in the world, known for its strength and durability. Cement is a crucial binding material used in construction, particularly in concrete. It is well known that cement production is not neutral for natural environment among others due to high CO₂ emission. Different strategies of mitigation of negative environmental impact of its production are developed. One of the ways is utilization of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) in the manufacture of cement and concrete. This study investigates the effect of polypropylene (PP) fibers on the mechanical properties and Workability of concrete incorporating lime sludge as a partial replacement for cement. Lime sludge, a by-product of various industrial processes, not only minimizes cement consumption but also contributes to waste management and reduced carbon emissions. Polypropylene fibers, known for their ability to control microcracking and enhance ductility, are introduced to counteract the brittleness associated with lime-based concrete mixes. Experimental investigations were carried out by replacing cement with lime sludge (5%,10%,15%,20%) while adding polypropylene fibers in controlled dosages (0.5%,1.0%,1.5%) by overall volume. Key parameters such as workability, compressive strength, split tensile strength, flexural strength and rebound hammer test (NDT) were evaluated.

Keywords: Concrete, Polypropylene fibres, supplementary cementitious materials, Lime sludge, Workability, Mechanical properties enhancement.

1. Introduction:

Concrete is the most widely used construction material due to its high compressive strength, durability, and versatility; however, concerns related to low tensile strength, cracking, and the environmental impact of cement production have encouraged the use of alternative and sustainable materials. The manufacture of cement is energy-intensive and is a major contributor to carbon dioxide emissions, creating a need for partial replacement materials that can reduce cement content while maintaining acceptable performance.

Lime sludge is an industrial by-product generated in large quantities by paper industries during the chemical recovery process. In this study, lime sludge obtained from the ITC Bhadrachalam Paper Industry, Telangana, is used as a partial replacement of cement in concrete. Utilization of this waste material not only addresses disposal and environmental issues faced by the industry but also contributes to sustainable construction by conserving natural resources and reducing the carbon footprint of concrete. However, concrete incorporating lime sludge may

experience variations in strength and cracking behaviour, which necessitates performance enhancement measures.

Polypropylene fibers are synthetic fibers widely used in fiber-reinforced concrete due to their light weight, chemical inertness, and effectiveness in controlling micro-cracks. The inclusion of polypropylene fibers improves tensile and flexural strength, reduces plastic shrinkage cracking, and enhances the durability and toughness of concrete. The combined use of polypropylene fibers and lime sludge-based concrete offers a promising approach to producing eco-friendly concrete with improved performance characteristics.

Although several studies have been carried out on the use of supplementary cementitious materials and fiber-reinforced concrete, significant research gaps still exist in the combined application of lime sludge and polypropylene fibers in concrete. Limited literature is available on the utilization of lime sludge, particularly sourced from paper industries, as a partial replacement of cement. Moreover, most studies focus on either lime sludge-based concrete or polypropylene fiber-reinforced concrete individually, with very few investigations addressing their combined effect. There is a lack of clarity regarding the optimum percentage of cement replacement by lime sludge and the appropriate dosage of polypropylene fibers to achieve improved mechanical performance.

Therefore, the present study investigates the effect of polypropylene fibers on concrete with partial replacement of cement by lime sludge sourced from the ITC Bhadrachalam Paper Industry, Telangana, focusing on the workability, mechanical properties and overall suitability of the concrete for sustainable construction applications.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENT DESIGN

2.1 MATERIALS

2.1.1 CEMENT:

OPC 53 Grade Cement was purchased from nearby vendors. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC 53 Grade) was used as the primary binding material in this study due to its high early strength, finer particle size, and rapid hydration, which enable meeting M30 grade concrete standards. It has a 3.13 specific gravity. As per IS 12269:2013, OPC 53 provides outstanding compressive strength, predictable setting times, and consistent quality. Its high C--S content ensures better bonding and compatibility with lime sludge powder in modified concrete mixtures.

2.1.2 LIME SLUDGE:

Lime sludge (LS) was collected from the ITC Bhadrachalam Paper Mill, Telangana, India, where it is generated as a by-product during the causticizing stage of the paper manufacturing process. The material primarily consists of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) and residual lime (CaO), with minor impurities from process chemicals. Prior to use, the sludge was oven-dried, ground, and sieved to ensure uniform particle size. Due to its high calcium content and fine particle size, lime sludge exhibits filler characteristics and limited cementitious or pozzolanic activity on its own.

When used as a partial replacement of cement, lime sludge contributes to the concrete matrix mainly through physical and chemical interactions with cement. The fine particles of lime

sludge fill micro-voids between cement grains, improving particle packing density and reducing porosity, which enhances the bond within the cement paste and at the aggregate–paste interface. Chemically, the calcium-rich lime sludge participates in the hydration process by providing additional calcium ions, which can support the formation of calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) gel when reactive silica is present. This improved microstructure strengthens the bond between cement hydration products and lime sludge particles. However, excessive replacement levels may dilute the cement content, leading to reduced strength, highlighting the importance of optimizing the lime sludge percentage for effective bonding and performance.

Constituent	Percentage by Weight (%)
CaCO ₃	70 – 85
CaO	2 – 8
MgO	1 – 4
SiO ₂	2 – 6
Al ₂ O ₃	0.5 – 2
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.2 – 1.5
Na ₂ O	0.5 – 2

Table1: Constituents of lime sludge

2.1.3 COARSE AGGREGATES:

Coarse aggregate with a nominal maximum size of 20 mm was used in M30 grade concrete and was purchased from nearby suppliers. The aggregate was made of crushed angular stone that complied with IS 383. It was free of contaminants like silt, clay, and organic impurities and was clean, hard, and long-lasting. The coarse aggregate had a specific gravity of 2.74. In order to achieve the necessary strength and durability of the concrete, proper grading of the locally sourced 20 mm aggregate improved interlocking, and effective bonding with the cement paste.

2.1.4 FINE AGGREGATES:

In this study, fine aggregate of Zone II classification was used, which was procured from local vendors. The fine aggregate consisted of clean, well-graded natural sand conforming to IS 383 and was free from deleterious materials such as silt, clay, and organic impurities. The specific gravity of the fine aggregate was 2.66. The Zone II grading ensured adequate workability, reduced segregation, and improved particle packing, contributing to the desired strength and durability of M30 concrete.

2.1.5 POLYPROPYLENE FIBERS:

Polypropylene fibers were used in nominal and modified mixes of concrete to enhance its mechanical performance and crack resistance. The fibers were supplied by the UltraTech RMC plant located at Raphadu and were uniformly dispersed within the concrete mix. The inclusion of polypropylene fibers helped in controlling plastic shrinkage cracks, improving tensile and flexural behaviour of the concrete.

Specific gravity	Fiber diameter	Fiber length	Tensile strength	Melting point
0.91	38 microns	12mm	300-400Mpa	160-170 °C

Table2: Properties of polypropylene fibers

2.1.6 Water:

Potable water that meets the standards set forth in IS 456:2000 was used for mixing and curing the concrete. The clean water is free from salts, oils, organic substances, and other impurities that could adversely affect cement hydration or the durability of the concrete. Employing standard water in both the control and modified concrete mixes ensures suitable workability, consistent strength development, and uniform hydration of OPC 53 cement.

2.1.7 Chemical Admixture (Superplasticizer):

In this study, a Polycarboxylate Ether (PCE)–based superplasticizer conforming to **IS 9103** was used to enhance the workability of M30 grade concrete incorporating varying proportions of polypropylene fibers and lime sludge. The PCE superplasticizer effectively dispersed cement particles, reduced water demand, and compensated for the reduction in workability caused by the inclusion of fibers and lime sludge. Its use ensured uniform fiber distribution and minimized segregation across all mix combinations. A constant dosage of **0.75% by weight of cement**, as recommended in IS 9103, was maintained for all mixes to achieve consistent fresh concrete properties.

2.2 EXPERIMENT DESIGN

2.2.1 MIX PROPORTIONS:

In the present study, M30 grade concrete mixes were prepared by incorporating polypropylene fibers at 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5%, of overall volume with four levels of cement replacement by lime sludge (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%) for each polypropylene fiber content. This resulted in a total of 12 different mix combinations, in addition to a nominal control mix without polypropylene fibers and lime sludge. The total cementitious content was maintained at 389 kg/m³ for all mixes, providing a consistent basis to evaluate the combined influence of polypropylene fibers and lime sludge on the properties of concrete.

Below table shows the all mix proportions

% of lime sludge	% of pp fiber	Cement (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	Lime Sludge Powder (kg/m ³)	Fibre (kg/m ³)	Super Plasticizer (kg/m ³)	Coarse Aggregate (kg/m ³)	Fine Aggregate (kg/m ³)
0	0	389	148	0.00	0.000	2.91	1137	799
5	0.5	369	148	20	0.5	2.91	1137	799
10	0.5	350	148	39	0.5	2.91	1137	799
15	0.5	330	148	59	0.5	2.91	1137	799
20	0.5	311	148	78	0.5	2.91	1137	799
5	1.0	369	148	20	1.0	2.91	1137	799
10	1.0	350	148	39	1.0	2.91	1137	799
15	1.0	330	148	59	1.0	2.91	1137	799
20	1.0	311	148	78	1.0	2.91	1137	799
5	1.5	369	148	20	1.5	2.91	1137	799
10	1.5	350	148	39	1.5	2.91	1137	799
15	1.5	330	148	59	1.5	2.91	1137	799

20	1.5	311	148	78	1.5	2.91	1137	799
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Table3: various mix proportions**2.2.2 MIXING AND CASTING PROCEDURE:**

For all concrete mixes, including the nominal mix and the twelve modified mixes, the mixing and casting procedure was kept consistent. The required quantities of cement, lime sludge (as partial replacement of cement), fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate were weighed accurately as per the mix design, with the total cementitious content maintained at 380 kg/m³. Dry mixing of cement (and lime sludge), fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate was carried out in a concrete mixer to ensure uniform distribution. Polypropylene fibers were then added gradually during mixing to avoid balling and to achieve uniform dispersion. Subsequently, the calculated quantity of water mixed with a Polycarboxylate Ether-based superplasticizer (0.75% by weight of cement, conforming to IS 9103) was added slowly, and wet mixing was continued until a homogeneous and workable concrete mix was obtained.

The fresh concrete was then placed into clean and oiled moulds in layers and compacted properly using a table vibrator to eliminate entrapped air. After casting, the specimens were finished smoothly and covered to prevent moisture loss. All specimens were demoulded after 24 hours and cured in clean water at room temperature until the respective testing ages.

2.2.3 FRESH AND HARDENED CONCRETE PROPERTIES:

The fresh concrete properties of all mixes, including the nominal mix and the twelve modified mixes, were evaluated to assess workability before casting. For hardened concrete, compressive strength tests were conducted on cube specimens at 7, 28, and 56 days of curing. Split tensile strength and flexural strength tests were performed at 28 and 56 days to evaluate the tensile and flexural performance of concrete incorporating polypropylene fibers and lime sludge. In addition, a non-destructive rebound hammer test was carried out on cube specimens at 7, 28, and 56 days to assess surface hardness and correlate it with compressive strength development over time.

3 Results and discussion:**3.1 General concepts of testing processes:**

All testing procedures in this study were carried out in accordance with relevant **Indian Standard (IS) codes** to ensure uniformity and standardization. The workability of fresh concrete was assessed as per **IS 1199**. Compressive strength tests on concrete cube specimens were conducted at 7, 28, and 56 days in accordance with **IS 516**. Split tensile strength tests on cylindrical specimens and flexural strength tests on beam specimens were also performed as per **IS 516** at 28 and 56 days of curing. In addition, the non-destructive rebound hammer test was carried out on cube specimens at 7, 28, and 56 days in accordance with **IS 13311 (Part 2)**. Compliance with these codes ensured accuracy, repeatability, and reliability of the experimental results.

3.2 Slump:

The slump test was carried out to assess the workability of fresh concrete in accordance with IS 1199. The slump cone used had a height of 300 mm, a bottom diameter of 200 mm, and a top diameter of 100 mm, and it was placed on a clean, level, non-absorbent surface. Fresh

concrete was filled into the cone in three equal layers, each layer being approximately 100 mm in height. Each layer was tamped 25 times with a standard tamping rod to ensure proper compaction. After filling and levelling the top surface, the cone was lifted vertically without any lateral movement, and the decrease in height of the concrete was measured immediately as the slump value.

Slump		
% of Polypropylene fiber	% of lime Sludge	Slump (mm)
0	0	92
0.5	5	82
0.5	10	79
0.5	15	76
0.5	20	73
1	5	79
1	10	75
1	15	72
1	20	69
1.5	5	75
1.5	10	72
1.5	15	68
1.5	20	65

Table 4: Slump Values

Graph1: slump V/S percentage(pp fiber & Lime sludge)

The slump test results indicate a consistent reduction in workability with increasing lime sludge replacement and polypropylene fiber content. For all mixes, the control concrete exhibited a slump of 92 mm, which gradually decreased as lime sludge content increased from 5% to 20%. At 0.5% polypropylene fibers, the slump reduced to 73 mm at 20% lime sludge, while at 1.0% and 1.5% fiber contents, the slump further decreased to 69 mm and 65 mm, respectively. This trend demonstrates that the finer particles of lime sludge increase water demand, and higher

polypropylene fiber dosage causes greater internal resistance and fiber interlocking, leading to reduced workability of fresh concrete

3.3 Compressive Strength:

Compressive Strength				
% of Polypropylene fiber	% of lime Sludge	7-days	28-days	56-days
0	0	26.70	38.19	40.26
0.5	5	26.82	38.43	40.78
0.5	10	30.02	39.56	41.32
0.5	15	24.29	33.61	35.79
0.5	20	22.45	30.01	32.25
1	5	28.02	39.72	41.82
1	10	33.02	41.56	44.44
1	15	26.29	36.61	38.62
1	20	25.45	33.01	35.35
1.5	5	26.76	38.25	40.74
1.5	10	28.19	39.44	40.92
1.5	15	22.16	33.63	35.07
1.5	20	20.25	30.88	33.23

Table5: Compressive Strength Results

Graph2: Compressive strength V/S percentage(pp fiber & Lime sludge)

The compressive strength results demonstrate a clear influence of both lime sludge replacement level and polypropylene fiber content on strength development at 7, 28, and 56 days. For all

fiber dosages, a gradual increase in compressive strength was observed up to 10% replacement of cement with lime sludge, indicating improved particle packing and a filler effect that enhanced the density of the cement matrix. The presence of polypropylene fibers further contributed to strength improvement by controlling microcrack propagation and improving stress transfer within the concrete. The highest compressive strength values were achieved at 10% lime sludge replacement with 1.0% polypropylene fibers, showing better synergy between fiber reinforcement and the cement–lime sludge matrix. However, beyond 10% replacement, a significant reduction in compressive strength was noted at 15% and 20%, which can be attributed to the dilution of cementitious content and insufficient binding capacity of excess lime sludge. This trend was consistent across all curing ages, confirming that an optimum combination of lime sludge and polypropylene fibers is essential for achieving improved compressive strength.

3.4 Split tensile Strength:

Split Tensile Strength			
% of Polypropylene fiber	% of lime Sludge	28-days	56-days
0	0	2.24	2.38
0.5	5	2.54	2.86
0.5	10	2.72	3.07
0.5	15	2.61	2.84
0.5	20	1.96	2.01
1	5	2.82	3.09
1	10	3.15	3.56
1	15	2.71	2.94
1	20	2.53	2.75
1.5	5	2.16	2.23
1.5	10	2.02	2.16
1.5	15	1.96	2.02
1.5	20	1.85	1.99

Table6: Split Tensile Strength Results

Graph3: Split Tensile Strength V/S percentage(pp fiber & Lime sludge)

The split tensile strength results at 28 and 56 days clearly show the combined effect of lime sludge replacement and polypropylene fiber content on the tensile performance of concrete. For mixes with 0.5% polypropylene fibers, the split tensile strength increased from 2.24 N/mm² for the control mix to a maximum of 2.72 N/mm² (28 days) and 3.07 N/mm² (56 days) at 10% lime sludge replacement, after which the strength decreased at 15% and 20%, indicating an optimum replacement level. A similar but more pronounced trend was observed for mixes containing 1.0% polypropylene fibers, where the highest values of 3.15 N/mm² at 28 days and 3.56 N/mm² at 56 days were achieved at 10% lime sludge, demonstrating effective crack-bridging by fibers and improved matrix densification. In contrast, mixes with 1.5% polypropylene fibers showed a continuous reduction in split tensile strength with increasing lime sludge content, likely due to fiber agglomeration and reduced workability leading to poor compaction. Overall, the results indicate that 10% lime sludge replacement combined with 1.0% polypropylene fibers provides the most favourable improvement in split tensile strength, while higher lime sludge or excessive fiber content adversely affects tensile performance.

3.5 Flexural Strength:

Flexural Strength			
% of Polypropylene fiber	% of lime Sludge	28-days	56-days
0	0	3.38	3.51
0.5	5	3.52	3.66
0.5	10	3.8	3.93
0.5	15	3.38	3.46
0.5	20	3.09	3.23
1	5	3.65	3.74
1	10	4.22	4.35
1	15	3.52	3.68
1	20	3.38	3.52
1.5	5	3.42	3.58
1.5	10	3.76	3.82
1.5	15	3.04	3.12
1.5	20	2.85	2.96

Table7: Flexural Strength Results

Graph4: Flexural Strength V/S percentage(pp fiber & Lime sludge)

The flexural strength results show an increase in strength with lime sludge replacement up to 10% for all polypropylene fiber contents at both 28 and 56 days. The maximum flexural strength was achieved with 1.0% polypropylene fibers and 10% lime sludge, due to improved matrix densification and effective crack-bridging under bending. Beyond 10% replacement, a reduction in flexural strength was observed at 15% and 20%, attributed to reduced cementitious bonding and poorer compaction. Overall, moderate lime sludge replacement combined with an optimum fiber dosage enhanced flexural performance, while higher levels adversely affected strength.

3.6 Rebound Hammer Test (NDT):

Compressive Strength (Rebound Hammer test)				
% of Polypropylene fiber	% of lime Sludge	7-days	28-days	56-days
0	0	21.63	31.32	32.61
0.5	5	21.73	31.51	33.03
0.5	10	24.32	32.44	33.47
0.5	15	19.67	27.56	28.99
0.5	20	18.18	24.61	26.12
1	5	22.7	32.57	34.29
1	10	26.75	34.08	36.44
1	15	21.29	30.02	31.67
1	20	20.61	27.07	28.99
1.5	5	21.68	31.37	33

1.5	10	22.83	32.34	33.15
1.5	15	17.95	27.57	28.4
1.5	20	16.4	25.32	26.92

Table8: Rebound Hammer strength test results

Graph5: Compressive Strength(NDT) V/S percentage(pp fiber & Lime sludge)

The rebound hammer test results indicate a trend similar to that observed in compressive strength development, confirming the reliability of the non-destructive evaluation. For all polypropylene fiber contents, the rebound strength values increased with lime sludge replacement up to 10% at 7, 28, and 56 days, reflecting improved surface hardness and concrete densification. The highest rebound values were recorded for mixes containing 1.0% polypropylene fibers with 10% lime sludge, indicating better quality and uniformity of concrete. Beyond 10% replacement, a noticeable reduction in rebound strength was observed at 15% and 20% lime sludge levels, which can be attributed to reduced cementitious bonding and lower surface integrity. Overall, the rebound hammer results showed good correlation with destructive compressive strength tests and confirmed the optimum lime sludge replacement level as 10%.

4 Conclusion:

Based on the experimental investigation, it can be concluded that the combined use of lime sludge as partial cement replacement and polypropylene fibers significantly influences the fresh and hardened properties of M30 grade concrete. Workability decreased with increasing lime sludge and fiber content; however, it remained within acceptable limits with the use of a

PCE-based superplasticizer. Strength properties such as compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength improved with lime sludge replacement up to an optimum level of 10%, beyond which a reduction was observed due to dilution of cementitious material. Among the fiber dosages studied, 1.0% polypropylene fiber consistently showed superior performance by enhancing crack resistance and stress distribution, while higher fiber content (1.5%) led to reduced workability and marginal strength loss. Non-destructive rebound hammer test results closely correlated with compressive strength trends, confirming the reliability of the findings. Overall, the study demonstrates that 10% lime sludge replacement combined with 1.0% polypropylene fibers is the optimum mix, offering improved mechanical performance while promoting sustainable utilization of industrial waste in concrete.

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